

Dactylosternum abdominale (Fabricius, 1792),
a new species for Slovakia from the Cerová vrchovina Upland
(Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae)

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Abstract – *Dactylosternum abdominale* (Fabricius, 1792) (Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae) is recorded for the first time from Slovakia.

Key words – water scavenger beetles, Sphaeridiinae, new country record, beetles, Palaearctic region

INTRODUCTION

Although most members of the family Hydrophilidae (Coleoptera) are aquatic, many species are terrestrial. One of them is *Dactylosternum abdominale* (Fabricius, 1792) (subfamily Sphaeridiinae), a small, 3.5–5.5 mm long species living in a wide variety of decaying organic material. It is a partially synanthropic species distributed throughout the Palaearctic Region from Europe and North Africa to China and Japan, including the Mediterranean and Atlantic islands (FIKÁČEK *et al.* 2015). The species has apparently been extending its range in Central Europe, as indicated by recent reports from Austria (SHUCH *et al.* 2006), Hungary (LÖKKÖS 2009), the Czech Republic (BOUKAL *et al.* 2012) and Poland (GREŃ & TARNAWSKI 2021).

The collected specimen was identified by the first author based on the work of HANSEN (1987).

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RESULTS

Dactylosternum abdominale (Fabricius, 1792)
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – Slovakia, Cerová vrchovina Upland, Hajnáčka, Pod deravým cerom, flight interception trap in oak wood, 311 m, 27.VI.–9.VII.2021, 48°13'44.502"N, 19°59'41.526"E, 1 male, leg. A. Balázs, det. R. Cséfalvay, deposited in coll. R. Cséfalvay, Rohovce.

Remarks – Our finding from Cerová vrchovina Upland fills the gap in the Central European distribution of the species. No evidence is available for a human-mediated spread. Unlike in the surrounding countries where the species was found in places affected by human activity (in a compost heap in Hungary, in a pile of rotting grain in the Czech Republic, in a bunch of rotten apples in Poland) (LŐKKÖS 2009, BOUKAL *et al.* 2012, GREŇ & TARNAWSKI 2021), our record comes from a relatively natural environment of a managed basiphilous thermophilous oak forest biotope.

Fig. 1. *Dactylosternum abdominale* (Fabricius, 1792), male, habitus in dorsal view
(photo by Jan Bezděk)

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